

Zeolite ZSM-5 from Paddy Husk Ash with and without Template

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Since 1972¹, high silica pentasil zeolite ZSM-5 has drawn enormous interest because of its structure, shape selectivity and catalytic properties. ZSM-5 possesses controllable number of acid sites, the nature and strength of which vary according to its modification, e.g. silica alumina ratio. These properties make ZSM-5 useful in many reactions like methanol to gasoline², cracking, xylene isomerisation etc. Argaur and Landolt¹ used NaOH as

alkali, reactive silica sol (Ludox) as silica source, aluminium salts and tetrapropyl ammonium bromide (TPA-Br) or tetrapropyl ammonium hydroxide as templating agent. A wide variety of templating agents have been used³ for the preparation of ZSM-5 zeolite which are very costly. A few publications are also available^{4,5} reporting the synthesis of ZSM-5 in absence of any organic cation. However, only meagre information is obtained

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regarding replacement of another costly ingredient—the reactive silica sol. The present work comprises the synthesis of ZSM-5 from a cheap and abundant silica source like paddy husk without using costly templating agent to render the process economical and technically viable circumventing the post synthesis calcination step required for the removal of the template.

Results and Discussion

ZSM-5 from paddy husk with TPA-Br: The XRD pattern of the synthesised ZSM-5 sample is presented in Fig. 1. XRD taken by Rich-Seifert's-MZ-III goniometer with Cu-K α radiation at 40 KV—30 mA. The lines are in complete agreement with those reported in literature¹, and indicating purity of the sample.

The FT-IR spectra (Fig. 2) showed characteristic structure sensitive bands^{6,7}. The optical density ratio of the bands at 449 and 547 cm^{-1} indicated a value of 0.797, where for a fully crystallised sample the value⁸ is 0.80.

The DTA-TGA results of the sample is presented in Fig. 3. The TGA curve indicated a weight loss of about 2% upto 573 K and 11.5% upto 873 K due to loss of moisture and decomposition of the occluded TPA cation respectively. DTA curve showed a sharp exothermic band at 573—873 K with maxima at about 723 K. The degree of crystallisation of ZSM-5 phase from the reaction mixture for different time interval has been depicted in Fig. 4.

It has been noted that crystallisation has been completed within 20 h of reaction. The reactivity

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction pattern of ZSM-5 zeolite prepared from paddy husk ash.

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectra in the framework region (300—4 000 cm^{-1}) of synthesised ZSM-5 from paddy husk ash.

of the silica sol, as shown by rapid rate of crystallisation, may be due to the presence of large amount of monomeric silicate in the solution extracted from paddy husk ash. Such reactive sol permits its use in synthesis of zeolite, such as mordenite⁹, ZSM-5¹⁰. Derouane *et al.*¹¹ showed that the crystallisation of ZSM-5 depends, apart from other factors, on the nature of silica source used.

ZSM-5 from paddy husk ash without template: The composition of the reaction mixture used for such synthesis has been presented in Table 1. The seed used for synthesis were prepared earlier using templating agent. XRD pattern and FT-IR spectra of the sample prepared using seed is shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. The degree of crystallisation with time has been presented in Fig. 4, which indicates that process of crystallisation has been accelerated and completed within hours of reaction. Acetone is not known to have any templating

effect in the synthesis of zeolites having pentasil structures, which is supported by experiments using acetone in place of TPA-Br and without adding seeds so the reaction mixture. But a combination of acetone and seed increased the rate of crystallisation to a great extent as manifested by the reduction in time. Narita *et al.*⁴ also reported similar observation. To study the effect of acetone, separate experiments were carried out under identical conditions and reactant composition containing both acetone and TPA-Br. It has been observed that the crystallisation was completed within 14 h of reaction. It may be assumed that acetone increases the fluidity of the system and thus makes easy and fast diffusion of the ZSM-5 species, crystallised at early stage, which act as nuclei and accelerate rate of crystallisation.

Fig. 3. DTA and TGA curves of ZSM-5 prepared with TPA-Br.

Fig. 4. Crystallisation curves of ZSM-5 from paddy husk ash as silica source.

Experimental

The paddy husk was obtained from a rice mill at Durgapur. A reactive silica sol was prepared by treatment of the paddy husk ash (obtained by calcination of the paddy husk at 773–973 K in a stream of air in muffle furnace) with 1 to 3M NaOH followed by filtration. A reaction mixture was prepared by combining silica sol, aluminium sulphate (E.M.; 98%), H₂SO₄ and TPA-Br in water (Table 1). The synthesis was accomplished in a non-agitated teflon lined stainless steel autoclave at 453–463 K under hydrothermal condition and autogeneous pressure for varying time from 3 to 20 h. The product was washed with distilled water, dried at 383 K for 12 h and finally heated at 823 K for 10 h to expell the occluded organic cation. Synthesis of ZSM-5 without using the templating agent was also performed employing paddy husk silica and using seed crystal of ZSM-5 (0.2–0.4 wt% of the reaction mixture), prepared as earlier, in acetone (Table 1).

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF REACTION MIXTURE FOR SYNTHESIS OF ZSM-5 ZEOLITE FROM PADDY HUSK ASH

Sample	SiO ₂	Na ₂ O	(TPA) ₂ O	SiO ₂	Temp* K	Time h
	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	SiO ₂	H ₂ O		
ZSM-5 with TPA-Br	70—120	0.42—0.72	0.04—0.065	0.020—0.022	453	20
ZSM-5 without TPA-Br	70—120	0.42—0.72	0 ^a	0.020—0.022	453	12
ZSM-5 with TPA-Br, 120 acetone	70—120	0.42—0.72	0.04—0.065	0.020—0.022	453	14

* Time noted from the moment when reaction mixture attained the desired temperature. ^a0.2–0.4 wt% seed crystal and acetone.

XRD pattern was taken on a Rich-Seifert MZ-III goniometer with Cu-K α radiation at 40 KV—33 mA, FT-IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 1720 spectrophotometer and DTA-TGA analysis on a Shimadzu DTG 30 instrument in air at a heating rate of 10 K min⁻¹.

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